

Role of Yogic Practices on State-Trait Anxiety of School Level Boxers

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was found out the role of Yogic practices on state-trait anxiety of school level boxers in a pre-post design. Researcher selected 50 male boxer's students (ranged 14 to 16 years) out of all the practicing boxing in Saraswati Vidya Mandir Sr. Sec. School, Aligarh (U.P.). They were divided in to two groups of 25 students in each group. One group named experimental group and the second group was named control group. The experimental group was conducted yogic practices program for 3 consecutive months (5 days a week) in the morning time. The control group was not given any program other than their daily routine activities. The data were collected from the both groups before and after the treatment program. Anxiety was measured by State-Trait Anxiety Scale (Dr. Roma Pal and Dr. Govind Tiwari) 1984. After pre and post-data collection of both groups, the experiment was statistically analyzed by using a paired sample T-Test. The result of this study showed that the experimental group significant improvement in anxiety level as compared with control group.

Keywords

Anxiety, Boxer, Yogic Practices.

Introduction

Yoga is an integral part of ancient Indian civilization; originate thousands of years ago from the Sanskrit word 'Yuj', meaning to join, to unite. Practicing yoga daily can make a person strong from a physical, mental and spiritual point of view. Yoga is also important for maintaining good health. Daily yoga practice is not only important for preventing various diseases, but is also very beneficial for maintaining positive health. It mainly improves the human body physically (immune system, muscular system, skeletal system and digestive system, etc.), as well as mentally (boosts self-confidence, reduces stress and anxiety, promotes attention and stability).

Yoga practices intends to balance the autonomous nervous system, which is responsible for regulating involuntary bodily functions such as heart rate and digestion, reducing anxiety, improving self-awareness, and enhancing emotion regulation through asanas, pranayama, and dhyana (Yoganidra) as focused practices of yoga (Goyal et al., 2014). Yogic techniques, which blend the mind and the body, are very effective in reducing stress and enhancing the quality of life which makes yoga a practical solution to improving mental health and resilience (Woodyard, 2011),.

Anxiety has an adverse effect on the physical and mental health of a person. A common emotional reaction defined in the context of an individual worrying, being nervous, or feeling apprehensive is anxiety, which can impact an individual's well-being or performance (Spielberger, 1966). Today most of the people suffer from anxiety which has a long term effect on their efficiency. In today's times, children are worried about their studies, sick people are worried about their illness and players are worried about their performance in sports.

Nowadays the level of competition in the field of sports is very high, due to which it is a big challenge for the players to perform while keeping themselves mentally and physically healthy. Boxing is a combat sport in which it is important for a boxer to remain mentally healthy along with physical health. Excessive level of anxiety adversely mental affects of the boxer. There are two types of anxiety: State anxiety and trait anxiety. State anxiety which is short-term and specific to a particular condition that an athlete experiences, and trait anxiety, which is more general and long-lasting, indicating a tendency to experience anxiety in various aspects of life, not just in sports.

Objective of study

The objective of this study was to investigate the effect of yogic practices on anxiety among school level boxer.

Review of Literature

Anxiety can be a big problem for sportspersons, especially those who participate in individual and combat sports. In a sporting context, anxiety can come as pre-competition nervousness, fear of failing or worrying about an injury, which can interfere with concentration, decision-making, and even motor functions (Weinberg & Gould, 2019). Players must be physically and mentally fit to perform well in sporting events. In many research studies conducted earlier by researchers, it has been found that increasing self-confidence through yoga practice has reduced the level of anxiety in players and

improved their performance. Fear of failure, stress and indecisiveness increase the level of anxiety among players and decrease their confidence. Previous research studies have found that increasing confidence through yoga practice reduces anxiety levels in athletes and improves their performance.

Many studies have tried to determine the effectiveness of yoga on athlete anxiety level. S Divya Lakshmi et al (2013) who discovered in their study that 8 weeks of yoga practices (including asana and pranayama) significantly improved anxiety and stress. Swati R. Gawaliet al (2013) conducted this study the effect of yoga on anxiety levels in working women and found that regular practice of yoga to significantly result on reduce anxiety level of working level.

P. Gomathi (2021) conducted a study, the researcher found in analyzing the psychological variables for three different training groups of Yoga practices and aerobic exercises for twelve weeks of training, the obtained results favored all the training groups on anxiety, stress, and self-confidence of school volleyball players (girls).

Smt. Radhika G. Milli (2022) conducted a study was effect of yoga and aerobic exercises on physiological and psychological variables of women athlete. The researcher found in twelve weeks of Yoga (Asana) has shown significant improvement on Physiological (Blood Pressure, Resting pulse rate, Vital capacity) and psychological (Anxiety, Stress, and Aggression) performance variable of the subjects.

Methodology

The groups are selected in a simple random manner and the study was conducted with pre-test and post-test. The total number of subjects (N=50 boxer) were randomly divided into two groups, each consisting of twenty-five subjects (Age 14 to 16 years old). The training program was determined in consultation with experts and implemented for three months. Regular training was given 5 days a week in the morning. After completion of the pre-test, based on the performance on the criterion variables; the subjects are placed in their yoga practice group in the morning session for twelve weeks. The pre-test and post-test scores were taken as data for statistical analysis. The Anxiety was measured by State-Trait Anxiety Scale (Dr. Roma Pal and Dr. Govind Tiwari) 1984. The paired sample t-test was used to determine the differences among the pre and post-test means for the data pertaining to the variable in this study. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Training Program

Experimental Group subjects were given selected yogic training program. They performed slected asanas, pranayama, kriya and yoga nindra as scheduled. The experimental group has been given 12 week of yogic practices on a daily basis in morning time 5 days in a week, including yogasanas, pranayama, kriya (trataka) and yoga nidra at Saraswati Vidhya Mandir, Aligarh, U.P. Control group was tightly under control without any special training. The control group did not join in any training program, except for their regular daily routine workout and physical education classes. Relaxation asanas (Shav & Makarasana) were performed in supine and prone position after complete each lying asana.

Analysis

Paired sample t-test was applied to investigate Anxiety of experimental group subjects and control group subjects.

Table 1: Pre-Post Comparisons of Experimental Group on state anxiety.

Data	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Error Mean	Difference	t-value	p-value
Pre	25	57.76	4.807	.961	3.880	4.282	.000
Post	25	53.88	5.718	1.144			

(Tabulated t-value = 2.064, Level of significance = 0.05, df = 24)

Interpretation: Results of the table 1 exhibit that the experimental group (t = 4.282, p = 0.000, p < 0.05) showed statistically significant mean differences exist between pre-test and post-test.

Table 2: Comparison of mean between pre and post-test of control group of state anxiety.

Data	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Error Mean	Difference	t- value	p-value
Pre	25	57.12	5.349	1.070	2.520	2.743	0.011
Post	25	59.64	6.191	1.238			

(Tabulated t-value = 2.064, Level of significance = 0.05, df = 24)

Interpretation

The table 2 shows that there is a statistically significant difference between the “Pre-test” and “Post-test” control group of state anxiety, with a p-value of 0.011 which is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Figure 1: Graphical-representation of state anxiety mean in control and experimental group in pre and post-test.

Table 3: Comparison of mean between pre and post-test of experimental group of trait anxiety.

Data	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Error Mean	Difference	t-value	p-value
Pre	25	60.76	3.982	.796	5.520	6.580	.000
Post	25	55.24	4.323	.865			

(Tabulated t-value = 2.064, Level of significance = 0.05, df = 24)

Interpretation

This table shows that there is a statistically significant difference between the “Pre-test” and “Post-test” experimental group of trait anxiety, with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4: Comparison of mean between pre and post-test of control group of trait anxiety.

Data	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Error Mean	Difference	t-value	p-value
Pre	25	58.00	6.124	1.225	.926	3.179	.004
Post	25	60.64	6.824	1.365			

(Tabulated t-value = 2.064, Level of significance = 0.05, df = 24)

Interpretation: The table shows that there is a statistically significant difference between the “Pre-test” and “Post-test” control group of trait anxiety, with a p-value of 0.004 which is less than 0.05 level of significance.

Figure 2: Graphical-representation of trait anxiety mean in control and experimental group in pre and post-test.

Findings

Discussion of Findings

The present study completed done to find out the effect of yogic practices on anxiety of school level boxer’s ranged 14 to 16 years old. There are many reasons for anxiety in a person, which include fear of failure, social comparison, low self-confidence, and competition pressure etc. It has been found in many research studies that daily practice of yoga has increased the self-esteem, self-confidence and reduced the level of stress and anxiety. Our finding are supported by **S Divya Lakshmi et al (2013); P. Gomathi (2021), Radhika G. Milli (2022), P. Kumaresan. (2012).** and **S.Rajesh (2023)** found out the interference of yoga practices to reduces anxiety, aggression and stress.

According to Swami Satyananda (2002), the state of Yog Nidra occurs due to the coordinated reaction of the hypothalamus. In this state, the activity of the sympathetic nervous system decreases and the activity of the parasympathetic nervous system increases, which increases the stability of the mind and a stable mind, develop self-confidence, which reduces the level of anxiety.

Due to over activation of sympathetic nervous system, breathing rate, pulse rate, blood pressure, heart rate increases, whereas due to activation of parasympathetic nervous system, there is slackness in behavior. Through asana, the important work of regulating breathing, heart rate and nerves through vagus is done, This approach allows for the easy and comfortable conservation of final postures, acting in the smooth and affable stretching of muscles, tendons, and joints. Due to which the entire nervous system comes under complete control, due to which excitement, anger, stress, anxiety etc. do not have a bad effect on the body and mind.

According to Hatha Yoga Pradipika, in chapter 2, it say that

चले वाते चलं चित्तं निश्चले निश्चलं भवेत् ।

योगी स्थाणुत्वमाप्नोति ततो वायुं निरोधयेत्।।

(H.P. Chapter-2, Shlok 2)

Conclusion

The body remains unstable as long as breathing continues and air moves in and out of the body. still, the exertion of the mind stops and becomes still when the breath is stopped or held. By rehearsing Pranayama, an existent can master the art of achieving deep attention and attention of the mind. When the mind and pran align harmoniously, it's nominated as Manoyog, leading to a remarkable improvement in tone- confidence and decrease the level of anxiety.

The results of this study show a significant mean difference between the pre and post test scores of the experimental group which is caused by the yogic interference. This indicates that the mean post test score has decreased after the delivery of the intervention in our experimental group as compared to the control group and this score is statistically significant. The result show that our experimental group has a significant reduces anxiety level before and after the test as compared to the control group.

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